

APPLICATION OF THE ANALYTICAL HIERARCHY PROCESS FOR SELECTING A MOTOR VEHICLE FOR TRAINING CATEGORY "C" DRIVER CANDIDATES IN THE MINISTRY OF DEFENCE AND THE SERBIAN ARMED FORCES

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Abstract: *The paper presents a case study on the decision-making process for selecting a motor vehicle for training category "C" driver candidates in the Ministry of Defence and the Serbian Armed Forces. Two vehicle alternatives (MAN TGL 12.180 and FAP 1118) were evaluated based on nine criteria defined by the study participants: vehicle stability, vehicle handling, visibility from the vehicle, cabin comfort, presence of dual controls, vehicle reliability, maintenance costs, fuel consumption, and purchase price. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), a method from the decision support methodology family, was applied, with emphasis on group decision-making and subsequent synthesis of individual priorities. The results of the group decision-making process favored the MAN TGL 12.180 vehicle.*

Keywords: *The Analytical Hierarchy Process, Motor vehicle, Driver training.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The functioning of a logistics system largely depends on the efficiency of its transport processes. Motor vehicle drivers operating heavy-duty vehicles represent a key resource within the transport component of large-scale logistics systems. The training process for acquiring the appropriate driving license to operate such vehicles is of strategic importance. The success of driver candidate training greatly depends on the conditions under which it is conducted, which in turn requires a suitable vehicle for instruction.

The subject of this paper is the selection of a motor vehicle for training category "C" driver candidates within the Ministry of Defence (MoD) and the Serbian Armed Forces (SAF). For this purpose, the Analytical Hierarchy Process was employed, one of the most widely used multi-criteria decision-making methods, applicable both at individual and group decision-making levels. The decision-makers (DMs) were driver training instructors from the MoD and the SAF Driver Training Center. The synthesis of individual decisions was carried out subsequently, by aggregating individual priorities using the Weighted Arithmetic Mean Method (WAMM) and the Geometric Mean Method (GMM).

2. AHP DECISION-MAKING

The Analytic Hierarchy Process was developed by Thomas Saaty in the early 1970s. The method is termed "analytic" and "hierarchical" because the decision-maker decomposes the decision problem into multiple decision elements and establishes a hierarchy among them. The hierarchy of the decision problem typically consists of several levels: the goal, criteria, subcriteria, and alternatives.

After the hierarchy has been established, the decision-maker performs pairwise comparisons of the elements at a given level with respect to each element on the level above, in order to determine their relative importance. In the standard AHP approach, elements are compared using linguistic (semantic) judgments of relative importance with respect to the element at the higher level, based on Saaty's scale from table 1 (Saaty, 1980).

Table 1: Saaty's scale

Definition	Numerical value (a_{ij})
Absolute dominance of element i over element j	9
Very strong dominance of element i over element j	7
Strong dominance of element i over element j	5
Weak dominance of element i over element j	3
Equal importance of elements i and j	1
Weak dominance of element j over element i	1/3
Strong dominance of element j over element i	1/5
Very strong dominance of element j over element i	1/7
Absolute dominance of element j over element i	1/9
(Intermediates)	(2,4,6,8)

When the decision-maker evaluates n decision elements at a given level of the hierarchy with respect to the element on the level above, using the scale from table 1, their semantic judgments (based on the definitions in the left column) are translated into numerical values (from the right column) and entered into a square matrix A . This matrix is positive and reciprocal (symmetric with respect to the main diagonal). In other words, the elements above the diagonal are reciprocals of those below it, and all elements on the main diagonal are equal to 1 ($a_{ij} = 1/a_{ji}$, for all i and j ; $a_{ii} = 1$ for all i), relation 1 (Saaty, 1980).

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

If the standard Saaty's scale is used, then each element a_{ij} can assume one of 17 values from the discrete interval $[1/9,9]$. The process of determining the weights of the compared elements based on the numerical values from matrix A is called prioritization. Prioritization is the process of deriving the priority vector $w = (w_1, \dots, w_n)^T$ from matrix where each $w_i > 0$ and the following condition holds $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$. There are several matrix-based and optimization-based methods for prioritization, however, in this paper, the additive normalization method (AN) was used due to its simplicity and frequent application. To obtain the priority vector w it is sufficient to divide each element in a given column of matrix A by the sum of the elements in that column (normalization), then the normalized values in each row are summed, and each resulting row sum is divided by the rank of the matrix n . This procedure is described by relations 2 and 3 (Saaty, 1980):

$$a_{ij}' = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}}, ij = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

$$w_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}'}{n}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Based on the evaluations, the selected prioritization method is used to determine the local weights of decision elements, through synthesis, specifically additive synthesis, the final weights of the alternatives on the lowest level of the hierarchy are calculated with respect to the element at the highest level (the goal), thereby completing the individual AHP decision-making process. Additive synthesis is represented by relation 4 (Saaty, 1980):

$$u_i = \sum_j w_j d_{ij} \quad (4)$$

where:

- u_i – the final (global) priority of the alternative i ,
- w_j – the weight of the criterion j ,
- d_{ij} – the local weight of the alternative i with respect to the criterion j [4].

In addition to prioritization methods, one of the key features of the AHP is that the consistency of decision-makers' judgments is verified at all levels of the hierarchy. To check for consistency, Saaty proposed the Consistency Ratio (CR), which is used in AN prioritization methods. Calculating the CR involves two steps. In the first step, the Consistency Index (CI) is calculated using the relation 5 (Saaty, 1980):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (5)$$

where:

- n – the rank of the matrix,
- λ_{max} – the maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix.

In the second step, the Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated as the ratio of the Consistency Index (CI) to the Random Consistency Index (RI), using relation 6 (Saaty, 1980):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (6)$$

The Random Consistency Index (RI) depends on the rank of the matrix, and its values are obtained by randomly generating 500 matrices, as shown in table 2 (Saaty, 1980).

Table 2: The values of the random consistency index (RI) depending on the rank of the matrix (Saaty, 1980)

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
RI	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.89	1.11	1.25	1.35	1.40	1.45	1.49	1.52	1.54	1.56	1.58	1.59

If the $CR \leq 0.10$, the result indicates that the decision-maker was consistent, and there is no need to repeat the evaluation. If $CR > 0.10$, the decision-maker should repeat (or modify) their evaluations to improve their consistency (Saaty, 1980; Jandrić & Srđević, 2000).

To combine individual decisions into a group decision in AHP, there are several methods, and in this study, the group decision was made by aggregating individual priorities (*Aggregation of Individual Priorities – AIP*), which is characterized by two aggregation methods:

- 1) *Weight Arithmetic Mean Method – WAMM*. Given the alternative A_i and its weight (priority) $w_i^{(k)}$ for the k -th decision-maker. If all group members (g) are assigned corresponding weights α_k , the weighted arithmetic mean is calculated according to relation 7:

$$w_i^{(g)} = \sum_{k=1}^m w_i^{(k)} \alpha_k \quad (7)$$

where:

- $w_i^{(g)}$ – the final (composite) priority of the alternative A_i ,
- m – the number of decision-makers.

Assuming that the individual weights α_k of group members are previously additively normalized, i.e.,

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \alpha_k = 1$$

- 2) *Geometric Mean Method – GMM*. In this method, the aggregation consists of applying relation 8:

$$w_i^{(g)} = \prod_{k=1}^m \left(w_i^{(k)} \right)^{\alpha_k} \quad (8)$$

The weights α_k of the group members are also previously additively normalized.

In both mentioned methods, a final additive normalization of the priorities of all alternatives is required.

3. FORMULATION OF THE HIERARCHICAL DECISION - MAKING PROBLEM

The hierarchy of the AHP decision-making problem is depicted in figure 1. The selection of a motor vehicle for the training of category "C" driver candidates in the Ministry of Defence and the Serbian Armed Forces is the goal of the AHP decision-making process and is positioned at the top of the hierarchy. At the next level are the decision-making criteria (C1, C2, ..., C9): vehicle stability, vehicle handling, visibility from the vehicle, cabin comfort, presence of dual controls, vehicle reliability, maintenance costs, fuel consumption, and purchase price. These criteria were predefined by the research participants (decision-makers) through survey questionnaires. The alternatives (A1 and A2) are at the lowest level of the AHP hierarchy, represented by the motor vehicles MAN TGL 12.180 and FAP 1118, which emerged as favorites based on the results of a survey conducted with the participants, among the vehicles available at the Driver Training Center in the MoD and the SAF (Ivezić, 2025).

Figure 1: The AHP decision-making hierarchy (Ivezić, 2025)

The group of decision-makers consisted of twelve instructors from the Driver Training Center in the MoD and the SAF, who are directly involved in the training process for category "C" driver candidates. Regarding the work experience of the instructors-decision-makers, 75% of the instructors had more than 20 years of work experience, 17% had between 10 and 20 years of work experience, and 8% had between 5 and 10 years of work experience (Ivezić, 2025).

The AHP was implemented by first familiarizing the decision-makers with the AHP decision-making problem hierarchy and the method of comparing hierarchy elements using Saaty's scale. Subsequently, they were provided with a form containing matrices for pairwise comparisons of the elements of the decision-making problem hierarchy.

4. RESULTS OF AHP DECISION-MAKING

According to the previously described methodology for conducting AHP, the results from the decision-makers' comparison matrices were processed using the Expert Choice 2000 (EC 2000) software. Table 3 presents the results of the individual evaluations of the decision-makers and the Consistency Ratio (CR) they exhibited.

Table 3: Individual evaluations (Ivezić, 2025)

DM	A1	A2	CR
DM1	0.640	0.360	0.02
DM2	0.753	0.247	0.03
DM3	0.562	0.438	0.01
DM4	0.686	0.314	0.06
DM5	0.670	0.330	0.04
DM6	0.661	0.339	0.04
DM7	0.479	0.521	0.02
DM8	0.683	0.317	0.03
DM9	0.692	0.308	0.02
DM10	0.443	0.557	0.03
DM11	0.494	0.506	0.05
DM12	0.720	0.280	0.05

The group synthesis of individual weight vectors was performed using the AIP WAM and AIP GMM methods. Both methods were tested for two types of weights assigned to the decision-makers, i.e., weights obtained by normalizing the reciprocal values of the decision-makers' Consistency Ratios ($1/CR$) and weights obtained by normalizing the ratings of their work quality (Rating), as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Variants of DM weights (Ivezić, 2025)

DM	1/CR	Rating
DM1	0.109	0.081
DM2	0.073	0.078
DM3	0.219	0.093
DM4	0.036	0.082
DM5	0.055	0.089
DM6	0.055	0.076
DM7	0.109	0.092
DM8	0.073	0.083
DM9	0.109	0.077
DM10	0.073	0.085
DM11	0.044	0.087
DM12	0.044	0.079

When the variants of decision-maker weights from table 4 are used for group AIP WAM and AIP GMM synthesis according to relations 7 and 8, the final priorities of the alternatives are obtained, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Group AHP synthesis

Since no change in the ranking of alternatives occurred during the dynamic sensitivity analysis (using the Dynamic option of the EC 2000 software) with a 5% variation in the importance of all criteria across all combinations, the final results of the conducted AHP can be considered stable (Hot, 2014).

5. CONCLUSION

The efficiency of the defense system largely depends on the quality of its personnel. Drivers of category "C" motor vehicles in the Ministry of Defense and Serbian Armed Forces represent one of the fundamental pillars of the logistical support system. Operating vehicles with higher payload capacities in specific, often complex conditions requires a high level of knowledge, skills, and psychophysical preparedness. In this context, their training process must not only be formally well-designed but also substantively tailored to real needs and modern standards of safety, effectiveness, and efficiency.

Successful training of driver candidates, in addition to pedagogical methods and quality teaching staff, largely depends on the conditions under which it is conducted, which also requires suitable motor vehicles for their training. This study demonstrates how the well-known multi-criteria analysis method - AHP, can be utilized to select an appropriate motor vehicle for training category "C" driver candidates in the Ministry of Defense and Serbian Armed Forces. The results of the conducted group AHP indicate that the MAN TGL 12.180 is the vehicle that should be used for the practical training of category "C" driver candidates in the MoD and the SAF. Its structural suitability for the driver training process, modern safety systems, high level of reliability, and comfort for both candidates and instructors make it preferable compared to other vehicles available at the Driver Training Center in the MoD and the SAF.

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